

METHODOLOGY OF TRAINING WRESTLERS' PHYSICAL QUALITIES

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Abstract. Mastering complex motor actions in wrestling is impossible without developing physical qualities. When developing a training plan, the coach can vary training for strength, agility, speed, and endurance, along with complex and simple technical-tactical actions, depending on the task at that stage, taking into account the individual characteristics of the athlete.

Keywords: circuit training, work capacity, intensity, physical qualities, lactate

At the present stage, a wrestler engaged in wrestling, regardless of the type of wrestling they specialize in, faces a lack of physical qualities. Some wrestlers lack endurance, others lack strength, speed, and others lack agility. The coach will always draw conclusions from a well-planned program for developing physical qualities and a well-structured training program.

Considering that the decline in work capacity is closely linked to the deterioration of the functional state of the central nervous system and the neuromuscular apparatus, the training methodology necessitates wider use in sports practice of exercises to improve coordination abilities as a mandatory condition for the development of spatiotemporal orientation (exercises with rapid head movements to different sides, left and right, body rotational movement, including with open and closed eyes, trampoline exercises, etc.), general and special coordination (turns, overturns, acrobatic exercises: walking on arms, rising, straightening, forward, backward, and side salto, performing coronal techniques from different grips and, especially, with competitive speed). This, on the one hand, will increase the stability of the analytical systems, which, in turn, will contribute to an increase in the stability of the central nervous system and an increase in its functional state and, accordingly, an increase in physical performance, and on the other hand, performing these exercises with the simultaneous development of other physical qualities will significantly increase the reserves of coordination capabilities not yet exhausted in this direction, on which the improvement of the effectiveness of technical-tactical actions in the match in competitive conditions depends.

To achieve a high level of work capacity in work of an acyclic nature, which is competitive activity in wrestling, it is extremely important to have a high level

of muscular aerobic preparedness (a large proportion of oxidizing muscle fibers).

The research results we obtained allowed us to formulate the main tasks that need to be solved during physical training:

- development of basic physical qualities;
- increasing the level of functional preparedness;
- mastering the permissible training loads.

The most effective organizational and methodological form of developing wrestlers' motor qualities is circuit training (CRT). The number of stations is determined by the number of athletes in the group. Each station can accommodate up to three athletes. One performs the exercise, two rest. The approximate time for continuous exercise execution is 20 s. During this time, athletes perform 10-12 repetitions of exercises with 40-60% weight. The rest time is 40 seconds. However, in any case, the optimal number of stations is 6-9. In this case, the duration of one round will be 6-9 minutes, i.e., the duration of the bout is modeled. The number of circles is 4-8 and depends on the stage of preparation and the preparedness of the participants. Physiological regimen for performing exercises: the number and intensity of exercises are limited by the pulse rate of 140-160 beats/min, and the rest time is restored to 120 beats/min.

To increase maximum anaerobic performance (MPA) and physical work capacity in young men, high-intensity lactate (6-20 s.) and glycolytic (30 seconds to 3 minutes) loads can be used, which must be combined with aerobic work of a restorative nature and aerobic-anaerobic focus (increasing overall endurance).

Only the integrated use of various intensity loads contributes to the growth of maximum aerobic and anaerobic performance of young athletes, increasing their physical performance. To prevent significant strain on the body, it is necessary to introduce active rest intervals of 7-10 minutes every 25-30 minutes during moderate-intensity loads and 15-20 minutes after high-intensity loads. Such pauses contribute to the rapid restoration of functions and an increase in the volume of work performed in this mode by 1.5-2 times. Between short high-intensity exercises, it is advisable to increase the rest intervals from 3 min. At the beginning of the series - up to 7-10 min. This contributes to performing loads at a high level of aerobic performance, a lower rate of lactate increase in muscles, and increases work time until the speed of exercise performance decreases.

When training athletes, it is important to plan training loads correctly. Competitive loads are the main ones in the training of athletes. All other loads

are of a supportive nature and should contribute to the maximum manifestation of physical qualities in a competitive exercise. However, without using basic training related to performing a large volume of diverse-oriented loads of a general and special nature with their optimal distribution in training cycles, it is impossible to achieve high sports results.

Intensive loads are also consistently applied in volumes of 7-10%, however, in the competitive cycle, at the stages of basic training and partially special training, a mesocycle can be conducted with the concentration of speed-strength-oriented means for 20-22 days. A mandatory condition of this planning option is the use of means for developing speed and strength in daytime training, and in evening training - the improvement of the technical arsenal. If special technical-tactical training precedes speed-strength training, the effectiveness of increasing speed and strength is minimal. With such a training structure, it should be remembered that to fully realize the effect of postponed training, 7-8 days of active rest and moderate intensity training after 3 weeks of concentration of speed-strength training means are required.

Then comes the 3-week stage of special technical-tactical training, during which loads are planned to be 25-30% less than in the concentration stage.

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